

Oral Presentation #12 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Varicella-zoster virus (VZV) is a neurotropic alpha-herpesvirus responsible for varicella (chickenpox) as a primary infection. Following this, the virus remains latent in dorsal root ganglia and can reactivate later in life, particularly with advancing age or immunosuppression, leading to herpes zoster (shingles). Herpes zoster typically presents as painful, vesicular eruptions following a dermatomal distribution. While the rash resolves within 1–2 weeks, pain may persist longer. This case report describes herpes zoster in a healthy 22-year-old female.

Case Presentation: The patient presented with a 3-day history of burning pain and erythematous, fluid-filled vesicles on the right chest. She reported mild fever (37.8°C), fatigue, and significant emotional stress in the previous month. She had a history of childhood varicella but no chronic illness or immunosuppressive treatment. Physical examination revealed grouped vesicles along the T5–T6 dermatomes and mild right axillary lymphadenopathy. Neurological examination was normal. Laboratory findings included mild leukocytosis and elevated CRP. Positive VZV IgM confirmed active infection, and VZV IgG supported past varicella exposure. Clinical presentation and dermatomal distribution helped exclude alternative diagnoses such as herpes simplex or contact dermatitis. The patient was treated with valacyclovir 1000 mg three times daily for 7 days. NSAIDs and topical lidocaine were prescribed for pain. By the third day, vesicles had begun to crust, and pain had significantly improved. By day 7, lesions had fully resolved without postherpetic neuralgia.

Discussion: This case emphasizes that herpes zoster can occur in young, immunocompetent individuals. Psychological stress likely contributed to VZV reactivation. Prompt antiviral therapy helped prevent complications.

Conclusion: Herpes zoster should be considered even in healthy young adults. Stress may play a significant role in triggering reactivation. Early diagnosis and antiviral treatment are essential for improving outcomes and preventing complications.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Herpes zoster, young adult, stress, antiviral therapy, dermatomal rash

INTRODUCTION

Varicella-zoster virus (VZV) is a neurotropic alpha-herpesvirus specific to humans. Primary infection causes varicella (chickenpox), after which the virus remains latent in dorsal root ganglia. With advancing age and immunosuppression, cell-mediated immunity against VZV declines, leading to viral reactivation causing herpes zoster (shingles). Herpes zoster is characterized by painful, dermatomal-distributed vesicular eruptions on an erythematous base affecting one to three dermatomes. While the rash typically resolves within 1–2 weeks, complete pain relief usually takes 4–6 weeks (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], n.d.; Gilden, Nagel, & Cohrs, 2014). This case report presents herpes zoster in a 22-year-old young female patient.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The patient was evaluated through detailed medical history, physical examination, and relevant laboratory investigations. Dermatological assessment focused on lesion morphology and dermatomal distribution. Routine blood tests including complete blood count (CBC) and C-reactive protein (CRP) were performed. Serological testing for varicella-zoster virus (VZV IgM and IgG) was conducted to confirm viral reactivation. A clinical diagnosis of herpes zoster was made based on typical cutaneous findings and supported by laboratory data. Antiviral and symptomatic treatments were initiated, and follow-up was conducted to monitor clinical progression and response to therapy.

RESULTS

A 22-year-old female presented with a 3-day history of burning pain in the right chest region, followed by the appearance of erythema and fluid-filled vesicles in the same area (Figure 1).

She reported mild fever (37.8°C) and fatigue. Her medical history revealed childhood varicella infection. She had no chronic diseases or immunosuppressive therapy. The patient reported exposure to intense stress during the past month.

Physical examination revealed grouped vesicles on an erythematous base distributed along the T5-T6 dermatomes in the right axillary region. Lesions showed typical dermatomal distribution. Mildly tender 1 cm lymphadenopathy was palpable in the right axillary region. Neurological examination was normal. Laboratory tests showed mild leukocytosis (WBC: $10.8 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$) with lymphocytic predominance. CRP was slightly elevated (12 mg/L). Positive VZV IgM indicated active infection, while positive VZV IgG supported prior varicella infection. The dermatomal distribution and characteristic clinical presentation helped exclude other vesicular rash etiologies like herpes simplex, contact dermatitis, and bullous impetigo. The patient was treated with valacyclovir 1000 mg three times daily for 7 days. NSAIDs were prescribed for pain control, along with topical 2% lidocaine gel. The patient was educated about lesion contagiousness. By day 3 of treatment, significant pain reduction and vesicle drying were observed. Complete crusting and healing occurred by day 7, with no postherpetic neuralgia developing.

DISCUSSION

This case demonstrates that stress may be a significant risk factor for herpes zoster development in young adults. Despite no evidence of immunodeficiency, intense stress likely triggered VZV reactivation. Early antiviral treatment prevented complications.

CONCLUSION

Herpes zoster can occur in young adults and significantly impacts quality of life. Stress management and early antiviral therapy play crucial roles in disease management. This case highlights the importance of diagnostic and therapeutic approaches for zoster in young patients.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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